

Amperometric Studies on the Composition of V(IV)-Ethanolamine Complexes

S. M. Fazalur Rehman and Anees Uddin Malik

Ethanolamine is known to form complexes with a number of heavy metal ions. In most cases these have been characterised by the method of chemical analysis¹⁻³ and little has been done to elucidate their nature and composition by physico-chemical methods. Only Michell⁴ applied spectrophotometric and polarographic methods for elucidating the structures of copper complexes of triethanolamine. It was therefore thought worthwhile to extend the studies to complexes other than those formed with copper.

Earlier results⁵ indicate existence of soluble complexes (greenish yellow in colour, of vanadyl chloride with mono-, di-, and tri-ethanolamines with absorption peaks at 650 m μ and 800 m μ) with a combining ratio of 2:3 (V⁴⁺: En) as found by the different spectrophotometric methods⁶⁻⁸. The complex was, however, found to be non-reducible at the dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) and therefore the polarographic method could not be employed. We were, however, able to apply the amperometric titration in this case. The results of these studies are described below.

Procedure.—Mono-(E. P., Naarden product), di-(E. Merck), and tri-ethanolamine (Naarden) were used during the experiments. Molar solutions of ethanolamines were prepared in double distilled water and were standardised pH-metrically against 1.0M-HCl. The strength of vanadyl chloride was determined⁹ after reducing it on a Jones reductor and titrating it against KMnO₄. The titrations (pH-metric) were carried out with a Beckman pH-meter, model G, with E type glass electrodes. The amperometric titrations were made with a Fischer electrode in conjunction with a multiflex galvanometer (type MGF2) in the external circuit. Before carrying out the titrations, the constant potential to be applied during titration was first determined. From the plateau of the polarogram (current-voltage curve) it was found to be -1.0 volt. Electrodes used were the dropping mercury and the standard calomel. Purified nitrogen was passed to maintain an inert atmosphere. The polarographic cell was kept immersed in a Townson-Mercer water bath, maintained at 30 $\pm$ 0.1 $^{\circ}$. Both direct (vanadyl chloride in the cell) and reverse

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(ethanolamines in the cell) were tried. Only the direct titration curves provided sharp inflections.

FIG. 1

- (i) 0.05M-VOCl₂ (10 ml)/0.2M-mono-En.
 (ii) " " (5 ml) / " -di-En.
 (iii) " " (" / 0.083M-tri-En.

The sharp inflections in the amperometric titration curves show the existence of 1:2, 1:3, and 1:2 complexes for mono-, di-, and tri-ethanolamine (Fig. 1) respectively. The results here do not confirm those obtained by spectrophotometry. The discrepancy may be attributed to two factors: (i) the instability of complexes under ordinary atmospheric conditions; (ii) the existence of colloidal precipitates. Since these factors would not interfere in the amperometric titrations (especially when the reactions are carried out in an inert atmosphere), this method is likely to provide more satisfactory results than those obtained by the spectrophotometric methods.

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